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Synthesis, Dielectric and X-Ray Powder Diffraction Studies of Iron(III), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Chelate Polymers with 2,5-Dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone

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Manuscript received 10 January 1990,
revised 5 September 1990, accepted 25 July 1991

IN continuation of our earlier work¹, we report here the synthesis of coordination polymers of Fe^{III}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone (DHBQ) and their characterisation by elemental analysis, ir spectra and magnetic moment data. The order of decomposition reaction and activation energies have been calculated from DSC. The electrical properties like dielectric constant and d.c. conductivities² have been measured. From dielectric constant, a.c. conductivities have been calculated. On the basis of X-ray powder diffraction studies cell parameters are calculated, the patterns indexed and the crystal symmetry determined.

Experimental

2,5-Dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone (DHBQ) was prepared and purified by literature method³. The metal salts used were acetates except Fe^{III} which was in the form of ferric chloride (AnalaR).

The metal chelate polymers were synthesised by mixing equimolar alcoholic solutions of the metal salts and the ligand. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 3–4 h and the solids separated slowly were filtered and washed with hot water and ethanol to remove unreacted reactants.

The elemental analyses were obtained from Regional Research Laboratories, Hyderabad. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer in nujol using CsI windows. Magnetic susceptibility was determined using Gouy magnetic balance. DSC was recorded on a Mettler T.A. 200C instrument. Dielectric constant (ϵ) and loss ($\tan \delta$) were measured at room temperature using a G.R. 1620 A capacitance assembly in conjunction with a laboratory built three-terminal cell.

An Argonic 72 external oscillator was used at high frequencies. For dielectric measurements the samples were made into pellets (1–1.4 mm \times 10 mm dia) in the frequency range 1–100 kHz. The conductivity ($\sigma_{a.c.}$) was evaluated using the relation, $\sigma = E_0 \omega \tan \delta$, where E_0 is the vacuum dielectric constant ω the angular frequency. The d.c. conductivity at room temperature was measured using a Kiethley 610C electrometer. X-Ray powder diffractograms were obtained with the help of a Philips powder diffractometer and the diffraction pattern was recorded at a chart speed of 2° (2 θ)/min using the scale 2° = 1 cm.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND MOLECULAR WEIGHT OF REPEATING UNITS

Sl. no.	Compd	Colour	Analysis % :		Mol. wt of repeating units
			Found/Caled.	C H	
1	DHBQ	Orange yellow	51.07 (51.42)	2.805 (2.857)	140.00
2	Fe-DHBQ	Snuff	37.43 (37.15)	1.37 (1.035)	193.84
3	Co-DHBQ	Maroon	36.48 (36.56)	1.22 (1.01)	196.93
4	Ni-DHBQ	Pale brick red	36.59 (36.62)	1.22 (1.01)	196.69

Results and Discussion

All the compounds are dark coloured and insoluble in water and in common organic solvents. They are stable at room temperature and non-hygroscopic. Elemental analyses of the compounds (Table 1) indicate the metal to ligand ratio as 1 : 1.

The presence of coordinated water in the polymer is manifested by a broad weak band in the high frequency region³ and it is further supported by the presence of a band⁴ around 700 cm⁻¹. The band at 3 290 cm⁻¹ (OH) was found in the ligand. The absence of this band in the spectra of the coordination polymers indicates the replacement of H by metal ion. A shift of C–O band to lower frequency further supports the participation of phenolic OH in coordination. Shift of C=O frequency in the ligand by ≈ 50 cm⁻¹ to lower frequency indicates the involvement of C=O in chelation. Further, the far-infrared spectra of the complexes show bands in the range 350–500 cm⁻¹ corresponding to M–O bands⁵. The tentative structure of the polymer is

assigned as

Magnetic moments of the Fe^{III}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} polymers are 5.88, 4.7 and 2.6 B.M. respectively, which favours high-spin octahedral geometry and their paramagnetic nature.

The electronic spectrum of the Fe^{III} complex shows a weak band around 23 000 cm⁻¹ assigned to ⁴T_{2g} ← ⁶A_{1g} transition, characteristic of octahedral geometry. The spectrum of the Co^{II} complex shows three bands around 13 000, 24 000 and 26 000 cm⁻¹ assignable to ⁴T_{2g}(F) ← ⁴T_{1g}(F), ⁴A_{2g}(F) ← ⁴T_{1g}(F), ⁴T_{1g}(P) ← ⁴T_{1g}(F) respectively, characteristic of octahedral geometry. The spectrum of the Ni^{II} complex shows two d-d bands around 16000 and 26 000 cm⁻¹ assignable to ³T_{1g}(F) ← ³A_{2g}(F) and ³T_{1g}(P) ← ³A_{2g}(F) respectively, characteristic of octahedral geometry.

From DSC plots, the order of the reactions and activation energies have been evaluated⁶. The activation energies for DHBQ, Fe-DHBQ, Co-DHBQ and Ni-DHBQ are found to be 9.15, 33.99, 31.11 and 14.64 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively. This shows that the coordination polymers are more stable than the ligand and the order of thermal stability of the polymers is as follows: Fe-DHBQ > Co-DHBQ > Ni-DHBQ.

Alternate single and double bonds present in the polymers provide a suitable channel for the flow of electrons and exhibit unusual electrical properties. Keeping this in view, d.c. and a.c. conductivities and relative dielectric constants of the ligand and complexes have been studied. For the ligand the loss is negligible throughout the range of frequencies. The d.c. conductivity of the ligand is low (7.87 × 10⁻¹² Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and close to that of a good insulator, however, its magnitude increases on chelation. The dielectric constants for DHBQ, and the Fe^{III}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} polymers are found to be 2.89, 12.54, 6.90 and 22.06 respectively. The dielectric constant values for all the polymers are found to be increasing with decrease in frequencies. The higher values of dielectric constant of all the polymers compared to DHBQ may be due to dipolar contribution.

The tan δ values are also found increasing with decrease in frequencies.

The X-ray (powder) patterns have been indexed by trial and error method keeping in mind the characteristics of the various systems till a good fit was obtained between observed and calculated sin² θ values. The unit cell parameters were calculated from the indexed data⁷. The diffractogram of the Fe^{III}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes consists of 15, 13 and 10 reflections respectively between 10 and 60° (2θ) with a maximum reflection at 2θ = 42.60°, 64° and 60.2°. The d-values for these polymer complexes were found to be 2.462, 1.445 and 1.535 Å at maximum reflection. The experimental values of the densities for these complexes determined by floatation method were found to be 2.57, 1.13 and 1.13 g cm⁻³. The observed sin² θ values of the Fe, Co and Ni polymers with 2,5-dihydroxy-p-benzoquinone fit well in the tetragonal system to give a unit cell with the lattice constants given in Table 2 alongwith calculated density values for n=4. The theoretical values are in good agreement with the experimental ones, which confirms the assigned tetragonal structure.

TABLE 2—LATTICE PARAMETERS OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	a Å	c Å	Cell volume Å ³	Density (theoretical) g cm ⁻³
Fe-DHBQ	7.445	14.180	785.968	2.560
Co-DHBQ	9.382	7.932	698.180	1.128
Ni-DHBQ	7.132	6.766	698.180	1.126

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